

The Change of Viscosity of Sols and of Precipitating Concentrations of Electrolytes with their Purity and the Change of the Ratio of Precipitating Concentrations with the Temperature of Coagulation.

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In a recent communication (Dhar and Gore, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 31) we have shown that the ratio of the precipitating concentrations of uni- and bi-valent and uni- and tri-valent ions with several hydroxide sols becomes less as the purity of the sols is increased. The same behaviour is also observed with the increase in temperature at which the coagulation is effected. We have extended our work to other sols and in this paper we are recording our results on the change of viscosity with the purity of ferric, stannic, ceric, zirconium, and thorium hydroxides, arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, cupric ferrocyanide, Prussian blue, uranium ferrocyanide, mastic and gamboge sols. We have also investigated the influence of temperature on the ratio of precipitation concentrations of uni- and bi-valent ions on some sols.

Ferric hydroxide sols.

A solution of Kahlbaum's ferric chloride was added to boiling water and a clear brownish red sol was obtained. The sol was kept in a parchment paper bag and was dialysed in hot water (80°-90°). As the dialysis progressed from time to time, a sufficient quantity of the sol was taken out and the purity, viscosity and ratio of the precipitating concentration were determined. The viscosity measurements were made in the same way as described previously (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 152, 393).

TABLE I.

Volume=5 c.c.		Time=1 hour.		Sol taken=1 c.c.			
The day of the hot dialysis.	Conc. of the sol (Fe_2O_3 per litre).	Amt. of Cl per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K_2SO_4 to coagulate.	Ratio of pptng. conc.	Viscosity at 30° (water=0.00803).
2nd. A	1.48 g.	0.7139 g.	2.07	2.5 c.c. 2N	0.5 c.c. N/100	1.000	0.00814
3rd. B	3.60	0.1511	23.82	2.0 c.c. N/10	0.2 c.c. N/100	100	0.00833
6th. C	4.28	0.1829	32.20	0.6 c.c. N/10	0.5 c.c. N/500	60	0.00847
8th. D	4.32	0.0465	90.80	0.2 c.c. N/10	0.4 c.c. N/500	25	0.00855
10th. E	4.32	0.03304	130.75	0.9 c.c. N/100	0.3 c.c. N/500	15	0.00938
11th. F	5.52	0.03300	167.20	0.4 c.c. N/100	0.2 c.c. N/500	10	0.00961
14th. G	5.18	Partly coagulated.		0.2 c.c. N/100	0.15 c.c. N/500	6.6	—

Stannic hydroxide sols.

Stannic hydroxide was precipitated by the action of ammonium hydroxide on stannic chloride solution. The precipitate on washing once or twice with water passes into a negatively charged clear sol, which was purified by hot dialysis.

TABLE II.

Volume=5 c.c.		Time=1 hour.		Sol taken=1 c.c.			
The day of the hot dialysis.	Conc. of the sol (SnO_2 per litre).	Amt. of NH_3 per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl_2 to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptng. conc.	Viscosity at 30° (water=0.00803).
2nd. A	18.24g.	1.0 g.	18.24	1.2 c.c. N	1.5 c.c. N/100	160	0.00868
3rd. B	18.24	0.6	30.40	0.5 c.c. 2N	1.0 c.c. N/100	100	0.00877
4th. C	18.24	0.4	45.6	1.5 c.c. N/5	0.9 c.c. N/100	35.5	0.01080
6th. D	22.92	0.2	113.6	0.7 c.c. N/5	0.7 c.c. N/100	20.0	0.01123
8th. E	5.96	0.03	198.66	0.6 c.c. N/100	1.0 c.c. N/1000	6	0.0572
10th. F	7.68	0.02	—	Coagulated itself.			

Ceric hydroxide sols.

30 Gm. of ceric ammonium nitrate were dissolved in 400 c. c. of hot water and filtered while hot into a parchment bag. The ceric

hydroxide sol thus obtained was purified by hot dialysis. The nitrate was estimated by colorimetric methods.

TABLE III.

Volume = 5 c.c.			Time = 1 hour.		Sol taken = 1 c.c.		
The day of the hot dialysis.	Conc. of the sol per litre.	Amt. of nitrate per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K_2SO_4 to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptng. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
3rd. A	24.96g.	15.5g.	1.61	2 c.c. 2N	3.9 c.c. N/100	102.5	0.00842
6th. B	44.76	0.62	72.1	1 c.c. N/5	3.0 c.c. N/100	6	0.0110
10th. C	131.7	0.246	531	0.5 c.c. N/5	3.0 c.c. N/100	3.3	0.0226

Zirconium hydroxide sols.

33 Gm. of zirconium oxychloride were dissolved in 400 c. c. of hot water ; to this solution ammonia was added drop by drop until the precipitate first formed just dissolved. The sol was purified by hot dialysis.

TABLE IV.

Volume = 5 c.c.			Time = 1 hour.		Sol taken = 1 c. c.		
The day of the hot dialysis.	Conc. of the sol (ZrO ₂ per litre.)	Amt. of Cl per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K_2SO_4 to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptng. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
<i>1st. preparation.</i>							
A	12.64g.	0.7420g.	17.3	0.5 c.c. N/5	0.8 c.c. N/400	50	0.0413
<i>2nd. preparation.</i>							
4th. A'	32.36	4.08	7.9	4 c.c. 2N	0.2 c.c. N/5	20	Very high.
6th. B'	28.40	3.27	8.7	0.6 c.c. N/5	0.1 c.c. N/5	6	
7th. C'	A jelly was formed in the bag.						

Thorium hydroxide sols.

A solution of thorium chloride (Kahlbaum) was boiled for about half an hour to increase the hydrolysis and was subjected to hot dialysis.

TABLE V.

No. of the sol.	Volume = 5 c. c.		Time = 1' hour.		Sol taken = 1 c. c.		
	Conc. of the sol (ThO ₂ per litre).	Amt. of Cl per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptng. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
A	14.12g.	1.020g.	13.73	—	0.4 c.c. N/5	>400	0.00839
B	12.96	0.6989	18.50	2.3 c.c. 4N	2.85 c.c. N/100	322.8	0.00842
C	0.92	0.0050	184.7	0.1 c.c. N/100	0.1 c.c. N/500	20	0.00957
D	Partly coagulated.			0.01 c.c. N/100	0.01 c.c. N/500	5	—

In the cases of ferric, stannic, ceric, zirconium and thorium hydroxide sols, the viscosity increases steadily with the purity. These results strongly support our view that as the electric charge decreases the viscosity increases. As the sol becomes purer and purer, the adsorbed electrolyte becomes less and the charge decreases. Along with the decrease of the charge the viscosity of the hydroxide sols markedly increased.

The above results show that starting with a sol which is not pure, and which contains appreciable amounts of hydrochloric acid in the adsorbed condition, the hydrochloric acid is removed steadily by hot dialysis and the sol becomes purer and purer, and requires smaller and smaller quantities of electrolyte for coagulation. When the sols become very pure and the amount of adsorbed electrolyte is extremely small, the viscosity is enormously increased though the concentration of the sol remains practically constant.

In order to strengthen our view that less the charge, the greater is the viscosity, we have carried on the following experiments. Highly pure and viscous sols of ferric, stannic and zirconium hydroxides were shaken with definite amounts of ferric chloride, zirconium oxychloride and ammonium hydroxide. These electrolytes act as

peptisers for the above sols. The following are the experimental results.

TABLE VI.

Ferric hydroxide sols.

Volume = 5 c.c. Time = 1 hour. Sol taken = 1 c.c.

Amt. of sol taken.	Amt. of FeCl ₃ solution to peptise (c.c.).	Conc. of the sol (Fe ₂ O ₃ per litre).	Amt. of Cl per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptg. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
50 c.c. of E sol.	5	5.48g.	0.2123g.	25.6	1.7 c.c. 2N	1.2 c.c. N/100	283.3	0.00837
E sol.	0	4.32	0.03804	130.75	0.9 c.c. N/100	0.3 c.c. N/500	15	0.00938
50 c.c. of F sol.	10	8.62	0.3713	23.2	1.5 c.c. 2N	1.4 c.c. N/100	214.2	0.00884
F sol.	0	5.52	0.0330	167.2	0.4 c.c. N/100	0.2 c.c. N/500	10	0.00961
19 c.c. of G sol.	10	11.02	2.504	4.3	2.2 c.c. 2N	1.7 c.c. N/100	258.8	0.00869
G sol.	—	5.18	—	—	Partly coagulated and highly viscous.			

TABLE VII.

Stannic hydroxide sols.

Volume = 5 c.c. Time = 1 hour. Sol taken = 1 c.c.

Amt. of sol taken.	Amt. of NH ₄ OH (4.25N)	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl ₂ to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptg. conc.	Viscosity at 30°
20 c.c. of E sol.	1 c.c.	3.5 c.c. N/10	0.45 c.c. N/100	77.7	0.00911
E sol.	0	0.6 c.c. N/100	1.0 c.c. N/1000	6	0.0579

TABLE VIII.

Zirconium hydroxide sols.

Volume = 5 c.c. Time = 1 hour. Sol taken = 1 c.c.									
Amt. of sols taken.	Amt. of Zr-oxychloride soln (c.c.).		Conc. of the sol (ZrO ₂ per litre.)	Amt. of Cl per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptg. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
40 c.c. of B sol, 1st preparation.	10	10	10.76g.	0.6273g.	17.1	0.5 c.c. N	1.8 c.c. N/400	111	0.0126
	B sol, 1st preparation.	0	12.64	—	—	—	—	50	0.0413

The above results show that the highly purified sols of ferric, stannic and zirconium hydroxides, which are highly viscous, can become much less viscous when their electric charges and stability are increased by the adsorption of the peptising electrolytes. Hence we have been able to establish definitely that by starting with impure sols the viscosity goes on increasing as the sol becomes more and more unstable and pure. On the other hand, starting with highly pure and viscous sols the viscosity can be decreased by increasing their charge and stability consequent upon the adsorption of the peptising electrolytes. Hence the relation between the stability and the viscosity appears to be a reversible phenomenon and can be established from both sides.

We have observed an interesting fact in the case of stannic hydroxide sol. The coagulum in the case of sols which were not specially pure and not highly viscous appears white whilst the coagulum obtained in the coagulation of the highly purified and viscous sols appeared almost transparent and far less white. This observation also proves the fact that with increased purity there is more hydration of the particles and hence the whiteness decreases.

In the case of sols of arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, Prussian blue, copper ferrocyanide, uranium ferrocyanides, mastic, gamboge, etc. no definite relation regarding the viscosity and purity could be established because these sols are steadily hydrolysed. But in the cases of antimony and arsenious sulphide sols it is seen that,

on the addition of hydrogen sulphide to both these sols, the precipitating concentration is appreciably increased. These results also prove that as the stability of the sol is increased by the adsorption of the peptising electrolytes, the ratio of the amounts of mono- and bi-valent ions, necessary for coagulation, also increases though in a much less marked manner than in the case of hydroxide sols.

Arsenious sulphide sols.

The sol was prepared as usual from As_2O_3 and then was subjected to dialysis at the ordinary temperature.

TABLE IX.

Volume = 5 c.c. Time = 1 hour. Sol taken = 1 c.c.

Sol.	Conc. of the sol. (As_2S_3 per litre).	Amt. of H_2S per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of $BaCl_2$ to coagulate.	Ratio of pptng. conc.
A	2.57 g.	0.17 g.	15.1	2.1 c.c. N/5	0.7 c.c. N/100	60
B	2.38	0.17	14.0	2.4 c.c. N/5	0.8 c.c. N/100	60
B peptised with H_2S	1.98	0.425	4.65	3.0 c.c. N/5	0.8 c.c. N/100	75
C	3.735	0.17	21.9	2.7 c.c. N/5	0.9 c.c. N/100	60

Antimony sulphide sols.

The sol was prepared from potassium antimony tartrate. The amount of potassium sulphate and hence potassium tartrate was found out by evaporating the filtrate after coagulating the sol with hydrochloric acid, and drying with concentrated sulphuric acid in a platinum crucible.

TABLE X.

Volume = 5 c.c. Time = 1 hour. Sol taken = 1 c.c.

No. of the sol.	Conc. of the sol (Sb_2S_3 per litre).	Amt. of K_2SO_4 per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of $BaCl_2$ to coagulate.	Ratio of pptng. conc.
A	5.45 g.	0.55 g.	9.9	0.9 c.c. N/5	0.8 c.c. N/100	22.5
B	5.53	0.55	9.10	0.86 c.c. N/5	0.75 c.c. N/100	22.3
C	6.325	0.55	11.40	0.85 c.c. N/5	0.75 c.c. N/100	22.2
C peptised with H_2S	7.6	0.80	12.6	0.9 c.c. N/5	0.5 c.c. N/100	36.0

Uranium ferrocyanide sols.

Dilute solutions of uranium nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide (excess) were mixed. The sol thus obtained was subjected to dialysis at the ordinary temperature, because by hot dialysis the uranium ferrocyanide sol is decomposed.

TABLE XI.

Volume=5 c.c. Time=1 hour. Sol taken=1 c.c.

Sol. (U-ferrocyanide per litre).	Conc. of the sol	Amt. of	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl ₂ to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptng. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
	(g.)	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ per litre.					
A	3.72 g.	2.54 g.	1.49	2.3 c.c. N	0.6 c.c. N/10	38.3	0.00868
B	2.42	1.47	1.65	1.0 c.c. N	0.3 c.c. N/10	33.3	0.00849
C	1.66	1.105	1.50	0.8 c.c. N	0.2 c.c. N/10	40	0.00837
D	1.44	0.929	1.50	0.8 c.c. N	0.2 c.c. N/10	40	0.00830
E	0.86	0.5892	1.49	0.8 c.c. N	0.2 c.c. N/10	40	0.00822

Copper ferrocyanide sol.

Dilute solutions of copper sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide (excess) were mixed. The sol thus obtained was subjected to dialysis at the ordinary temperature.

TABLE XII.

Volume=5 c.c. Time=1 hour. Sol taken=1 c.c.

Sol.	Conc. of the sol	Amt. of	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl ₂ to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptng. conc.
	(Cu-ferrocyanide per litre).	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ per litre.				
A	7.82 g.	22.09 g.	0.35	2.0 c.c. N/100	1.0 c.c. N/100	2
B	11.16	11.73	0.99	0.5 c.c. N/5	1.4 c.c. N/100	8.9

Prussian blue.

Dilute solutions of ferric chloride and potassium ferrocyanide (excess) were mixed. In order to help the peptisation a small amount of oxalic acid was used. The sol thus obtained was subjected to dialysis at the ordinary temperature.

TABLE XIII.

Volume=5 c.c. Time=1 hour. Sol taken=1 c.c.

Sol.	Conc. of the sol (Fe ₂ O ₃ per litre).	Amt. of K ₂ Fe(CN) ₆ per litre.	Purity.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl ₂ to coagulate.	Ratio of the ppt. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
A	16.46 g.	17.82 g.	0.92	0.5 c.c. 2N	0.5 c.c. N	3	0.01013
B	7.48	15.26	0.37	0.2 c.c. N/5	1.5 c.c. N/100	2.6	0.01267
C	7.52	19.89	0.48	0.2 c.c. N/5	1.5 c.c. N/100	2.6	0.01144
D	4.24	12.52	0.38	0.2 c.c. N/5	1.5 c.c. N/100	2.6	—

Mastic sols.

About 10 gm. of mastic were dissolved in 200 c.c. of alcohol. The solution was poured into distilled water drop by drop and stirred well. The sol thus obtained was subjected to dialysis at the ordinary temperature.

TABLE XIV.

Volume=5 c.c. Time=1 hour. Sol taken=1 c.c.

Sol.	Conc. of the sol per litre.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl ₂ to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptng. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
Not dialysed ...	1.96	1.4 c.c. 2N	1.8 c.c. N/10	15.5	0.01012 (high viscosity due to alcohol.)
Dialysed ...					
A	1.94	1.4 c.c. 2N	1.8 c.c. N/10	15.5	0.00826
B	1.80	1.4 c.c. 2N	1.8 c.c. N/10	15.5	0.00818

Gamboge sols.

5 Gm. of powdered gamboge dissolved in alcohol were poured drop by drop into 500 c.c. of water. The sol thus obtained was subjected to dialysis at the ordinary temperature.

TABLE XV.

Volume=5 c.c. Time=1 hour. Sol taken=1 c.c.

Sol.	Conc. of the sol per litre.	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl ₂ to coagulate.	Ratio of the pptng. conc.	Viscosity at 30°.
A	2.84 g.	2.3 c.c. N	0.7 c.c. N/10	32.8	0.00835
B	3.70	2.2 c.c. N	0.7 c.c. N/10	31.4	0.00829
C	3.56	2.2 c.c. N	0.7 c.c. N/10	31.4	0.00834

The coagulation of some of hydroxide sols are carried on at 60° in order to find out the influence of temperature on the ratio of the precipitating concentration of mono- and bi-valent ions. The experimental results are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE XVI.

Ferric hydroxide sols.

Volume = 5 c.c., Time = 1 hour. Sol taken = 1 c.c.

Sol.	At 30°		Ratio of the pptng. conc. at 30° (a)	At 60°		Ratio of the pptng. conc. at 60° (b)	a : b
	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.		Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.		
Sol A	2.5 c.c. 2N	0.5 c.c. N/100	1000	1.4 c.c. 2N	0.4 c.c. N/100	700	1 : 0.7
Sol B	2.0 c.c. N/10	0.2 c.c. N/100	100	0.7 c.c. N/5	1.0 c.c. N/500	70	1 : 0.7
Sol D	0.2 c.c. N/10	0.4 c.c. N/500	25	0.05 c.c. N/5	0.3 c.c. N/500	16.6	1 : 0.66
Sol E + 5 c.c. FeCl ₃	1.7 c.c. 2N	1.2 c.c. N/100	283.3	2.4 c.c. N	1.2 c.c. N/100	200	1 : 0.705
Sol F + 5 c.c. FeCl ₃	1.5 c.c. 2N	1.4 c.c. N/100	214.2	2.1 c.c. N	1.4 c.c. N/100	150	1 : 0.7002

TABLE XVII.

Zirconium hydroxide sols.

Sol.	At 30°		Ratio of the pptng. conc. at 30° (a)	At 60°		Ratio of the pptng. conc. at 60° (b)	a : b.
	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.		Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.		
Sol A	0.4 c.c. 2N	0.2 c.c. N/5	20	0.3 c.c. N	0.09 c.c. N/5	16.6	1 : 0.33
Sol B	0.6 c.c. N/5	0.1 c.c. N/5	6	0.5 c.c. N/5	2.0 c.c. N/100	5	1 : 0.833

TABLE XVIII.

Ceric hydroxide sols.

Sol.	At 30°		Ratio of the pptng conc. at 30° (a)	At 60°		Ratio of the pptng. conc. at 60° (b)	a : b.
	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.		Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of K ₂ SO ₄ to coagulate.		
Sol A	2.0 c.c. 2N	3.9 c.c. N/100	102.5	1.8 c.c. N	3.6 c.c. N/100	50	1 : 0.49
Sol B	1.0 c.c. N/5	3.0 c.c. N/100	6	0.4 c.c. N/5	2.9 c.c. N/100	3.1	1 : 0.5

TABLE XIX.

Stannic hydroxide sols.

Sol.	At 30°		Ratio of the pptng. conc. at 30° (a)	At 60°		Ratio of the pptng. conc. at 60° (b)	a : b
	Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl ₂ to coagulate.		Amt. of KCl to coagulate.	Amt. of BaCl ₂ to coagulate.		
Sol A	1.2 c.c. 2N	1.5 c.c. N/100	160	1.2 c.c. N	0.8 c.c. N/100	150	1 : 0.9
Sol B	0.5 c.c. 2N	1.0 c.c. N/100	100	0.75 c.c. N	0.8 c.c. N/100	93.75	1 : 0.9
Sol C	1.5 c.c. N/5	0.9 c.c. N/100	35.5	0.70 c.c. N/5	0.6 c.c. N/100	23.3	1 : 0.7

The above experimental results show that as the temperature is increased the ratio of the precipitation concentrations becomes less.

One thing, however, comes out prominently namely that these ratios change in such a way that the ratio of the precipitation concentrations at 30° to 60° is equal to constant, irrespective of the purity of the sol.

Summary.

1. The experimental results obtained in the viscosity measurements with sols of ferric, stannic, ceric, zirconium and thorium hydroxides of different degrees of purity show that the viscosity of these sols increases steadily with their purity, even when their concentrations are practically constant.

2. When these hydroxide sols are very pure and unstable and the amount of adsorbed electrolyte is very small, their viscosities are enormously increased.

3. Experimental results show that highly purified sols of ferric, stannic and zirconium hydroxides become less viscous when their electric charges and stability are increased by the adsorption of peptising electrolytes.

4. The coagulum obtained from a sol of stannic hydroxide which is not specially pure and is not lightly viscous, is white; whilst the coagulum with a highly purified and viscous sol of stannic hydroxide is almost transparent and far less white.

5. Hence it appears that increased purity of a sol is associated with greater hydration and greater viscosity. These experimental results strengthen our view that the less the charge on a sol, the greater its viscosity.

6. Experimental results obtained with all the hydroxide sols show that the ratio of the precipitating concentrations of uni- and bi-valent ions decreases as the purity and the viscosity of the sols increases.

7. No definite relation regarding the viscosity and purity of the sols could be established with sols of arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, Prussian blue, cupric ferrocyanide, uranium ferrocyanide, mastic and gamboge, since all these sols are steadily hydrolysed on dialysis.

8. On increasing the temperature of coagulation, the ratio of the precipitating concentrations of uni- and bi-valent ions with ferric, ceric, and stannic hydroxide sols become less; but these ratios change in such a way that the ratio of the values at 30° and 60° remains constant irrespective of the purity of the sols.